

Estimation of Neutron-Induced Fission Product Yield Uncertainties from Gamma Spectra Data with Bayesian Inverse UQ

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ABSTRACT

The fission product yields (FPYs) in ENDF/B libraries have been largely unchanged since the early 1990's. The current independent FPYs show high relative uncertainties, with many of these uncertainties established by the evaluators' best estimation. This FPY data is important to many modeling and simulation tools used throughout multiple nuclear disciplines. One particular application of interest involves rapid classification of fission type in post-detonation scenarios. Classifiers capable of identifying fissile material type and neutron energy spectrum from radionuclide activities measured by gamma spectroscopy have been developed. These classifiers have been shown to lose effectiveness in classification accuracy with increasing uncertainties in model parameters. As the models are reliant on FPYs, improving these uncertainties will provide more confidence in the classification predictions leading to more informed decisions. This work uses a Bayesian inverse Uncertainty Quantification (IUQ) methodology to quantify uncertainties in FPYs. Bayesian IUQ identifies calibration parameter distributions which produce model predictions in agreement with experimental data. Serpent burnup models and Gamma Detector Response and Analysis Software - Detector Response Function (GADRAS-DRF) models are employed alongside a set of gamma spectra measurements of irradiated fissionable specimens. The computational burden of the IUQ process is reduced through fast and accurate machine learning-based surrogate models.

Keywords: Inverse Uncertainty Quantification, Fission Product Yield Uncertainty, Nuclear Data Adjustment, Bayesian Calibration, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear forensics community has strong interest in the improvement of FPY uncertainties in the current nuclear data libraries, motivated by the need to rapidly classify fissile material and neutron spectrum in post-detonation scenarios. It has been shown that the specific activities of certain radionuclides can be used to classify fissile material and neutron spectrum from fallout samples collected within hours of a nuclear detonation [1]. The energy distribution of fission neutrons generally follows a Watt distribution with a mean energy near 2 MeV and a mode near 0.75 MeV. However, a nuclear chain reaction can be enhanced with neutrons produced from fusion of Deuterium and Tritium which produces a ~ 14 MeV neutron. Because the FPY of specific radionuclides differs depending on the fissile material and neutron energy spectrum, the resulting fallout particles will have slightly different compositions. This is demonstrated in the separation of mass yield curves near atomic masses of 105 and 155 shown in Fig. 1 using data from ENDF/B-VIII.0 [2]. Radionuclides with the largest differences in FPY and sufficient activity can produce unique signatures useful to a classifier.

As experimental data from actual nuclear fallout is extremely limited, the data used to construct the classifier was simulated using the Defense Land Fallout Interpretive Code (DELFI) with the Korts and Norman thermodynamic fractionation model. This model simulated nuclear explosions and the resulting fallout to identify 12 radionuclides deposited into fallout particles with sufficient differences in FPY

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Figure 1. Separation in FPY by material and neutron energy demonstrated in Mass yield curves of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu for 0.5 MeV and 14 MeV neutrons from ENDF/B-VIII.0.

for the resulting activity to classify fissile material and neutron spectrum. A sensitivity analysis of the model predicted specific activity showed that increased uncertainties in the input parameters created sufficient variance in predictions to reduce classification effectiveness [1]. The importance of FPY uncertainties in this process is compounded by the large uncertainties currently provided in nuclear data libraries. The relative uncertainties of independent FPY shown in Fig. 2 are above 50% in most cases with many placed precisely at 64%. This was the result of nuclear data evaluators assuming large uncertainties when experimental data was not available. Such large uncertainties will likely impact the effectiveness of a classifier that is reliant on accurate predictions using FPY as input parameters.

Figure 2. Large relative uncertainty of independent FPY will propagate to larger uncertainties in model predictions. Data from ENDF/B-VIII.0.

Current FPY data in ENDF/B is primarily derived from the seminal work [3] which was included in the ENDF/B-VI library. Since then, only two major improvements have been included in the ENDF/B library. Major improvements to the ^{239}Pu FPY were included in ENDF/B-VII.1 which introduced FPY for 2 MeV incident neutrons and reduced uncertainties in the 0.5 MeV and 14 MeV energies. The most recent release of ENDF/B-VIII.1 saw updates in 17 cumulative FPY uncertainties, 2 independent FPY values, and corrections to cumulative and independent FPY for ^{241}Pu with thermal neutrons. Independent FPY relative uncertainties in the Japanese Evaluated Nuclear Data Library (JENDL) resemble those in ENDF/B. While the Joint Evaluated Fission and Fusion (JEFF) library has made improvements to FPY data, even including covariance information, independent FPY relative uncertainties might be improved. Therefore, there is a need to more accurately estimate and thus reduce the FPY uncertainties using nuclear data adjustment methods.

Nuclear data adjustment methods are well established in nuclear criticality applications. Methods such as Generalized Linear Least Squares (GLLS) [4], Monte Carlo Bayes (MOCABA) [5, 6], and Bayesian

Monte Carlo (BMC) [7] are being extended to FPY applications [8]. These nuclear data adjustment methods identify the nuclear data distributions which produce model predictions consistent with experimental data. Using experimental gamma spectra data alongside radiation transport codes could lead to more directly informed independent FPY, which are typically derived from cumulative FPY and rarely measured directly. This work proposes to adapt the modular Bayesian approach for IUQ to nuclear data adjustments of independent FPY. Bayesian IUQ was originally developed and demonstrated in nuclear thermal-hydraulics [9] and fuel performance problems. It employs Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) to sample empirical posterior parameter distributions. The computational burden of MCMC is reduced through Machine Learning (ML)-based surrogate models while accounting for the introduce interpolation uncertainty.

2. METHODS

A detailed description of the modular Bayesian approach-based IUQ methodology is available in [9]. This section will only provide a brief summary due to the page limit. Nuclear data adjustment can be treated as an inverse problem involving a model with experimental data, as defined below:

$$\mathbf{y}_E(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{y}_M(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{y}_E is the experimental observation, \mathbf{y}_M is the model response, \mathbf{x} is the vector of design variables, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the vector of model calibration parameters to be adjusted, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the vector of measurement errors. The design variables \mathbf{x} represent elements of the experimental design such as geometry, materials, and operating conditions used to collect the experimental data. The calibration parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are specific to the model and might represent physical constants or model tuning parameters without a physical interpretation. This is an inverse problem because we are trying to describe the calibration parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ using observed experimental data \mathbf{y}_E . The formulation of the inverse problem in Eq. (1) assumes the model perfectly predicts reality at the true parameter values of $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. This framing does not consider differences between the model \mathbf{y}_M and the unknown reality \mathbf{y}_R . Including model bias $\boldsymbol{\delta}(\mathbf{x})$ addresses inaccuracies in the model due to improper physics or numerical approximations.

$$\mathbf{y}_E(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{y}_R(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad \text{where} \quad \mathbf{y}_R(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{y}_M(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \boldsymbol{\delta}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (2)$$

Combining the equations in Eq. (2) yields the model updating equation as the starting point for IUQ:

$$\mathbf{y}_E(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{y}_M(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \boldsymbol{\delta}(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

Bayes' Theorem in Eq. (4) provides a natural framework for the inverse problem.

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M) = \frac{p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M)} = \frac{p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\int p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot d\boldsymbol{\theta}} \quad (4)$$

where $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M)$ is the posterior, $p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the likelihood, $p(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the prior, and $\int p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot d\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the marginal likelihood, also referred to as the evidence term or simply the normalizing constant. The computational strategy is to use MCMC to sample directly from the posterior distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M)$. Because the marginal likelihood in Eq. (4) is not dependent on the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, it will be canceled in MCMC evaluations of sample acceptance criteria and we can rewrite:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta} | \mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M) \propto p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (5)$$

The prior parameter distribution $p(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ represents prior knowledge of the calibration parameters. When experimental data is limited, the prior's influence on the posterior is stronger relative to likelihood's. As a result, selection of the prior grows more important as the availability of experimental data decreases.

For nuclear data, the prior is representative of information available in the nuclear data libraries and is often taken to be distributed multivariate normal. However, this can lead to non-physical negative values. The log-normal distribution has been previously proposed to prevent this issue. An alternative is the beta distribution or its multivariate generalization the Dirichlet distribution. This distribution naturally has support from 0 to 1 and a special case of the distribution is a uniform distribution over the same support.

In order to form the likelihood $p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta})$, we assume the measurement errors are distributed zero-mean multivariate normal $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = (\mathbf{y}_E - \mathbf{y}_M - \boldsymbol{\delta}) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$. This implies that the measured data are normally distributed about the model $\mathbf{y}_E \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{y}_M + \boldsymbol{\delta}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ and the likelihood can be written as:

$$p(\mathbf{y}_E, \mathbf{y}_M | \boldsymbol{\theta}) \propto |\boldsymbol{\Sigma}|^{-1/2} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y}_E - \mathbf{y}_M - \boldsymbol{\delta})^\top \boldsymbol{\Sigma}^{-1} (\mathbf{y}_E - \mathbf{y}_M - \boldsymbol{\delta}) \right] \quad (6)$$

where the total variance is defined as $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{exp}} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{code}} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{bias}}$. The $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{exp}}$ term accounts for measurement error, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{code}}$ accounts for the code or interpolation uncertainty introduced by the surrogate model, and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{bias}}$ accounts for the model uncertainty due to model bias. A ML-based surrogate model can be used to significantly reduce the computational cost during MCMC sampling. If the full model is used directly by the MCMC sampler, the $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{code}}$ term is not needed. Similarly, if the model bias term is not considered then $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\text{bias}}$ are neglected at the risk of over-fitting in the posterior distributions to the chosen measurement data. This is because in this case, the model is assumed to predict the reality $\mathbf{y}_R = \mathbf{y}_M$.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DATA DESCRIPTION

The Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) maintains gamma spectra data collected from fissionable specimens irradiated in various neutron energy spectra [10]. One of the primary goals of the experiment was to compile a set of complex gamma spectra resulting from unseparated short lived fission products rapidly after irradiation. The experiments examined 3 specimens each of 5 materials irradiated under 4 neutron energy spectra as indicated in Table I. Thermal, epithermal, and fission neutron energy spectra were achieved in the Washington State University (WSU) Training, Research, Isotopes, General Atomics (TRIGA) reactor with specimens irradiated bare, cadmium shielded, and boron shielded respectively. The 14 MeV experiments were completed with a Deuterium-Tritium neutron generator at PNNL with significantly reduced fluence compared to the TRIGA reactor.

Table I. Materials and neutron energy spectra of experiments completed.

Specimens	Thermal	Epithermal	Fission	14 MeV
²³³ U	✓	✓	✓	
²³⁵ U	✓	✓	✓	
²³⁸ U		✓	✓	✓
²³⁷ Np		✓	✓	
²³⁹ Pu	✓	✓	✓	

Following irradiation, the packages were removed and the specimens separated. The first specimen was sent for immediate gamma spectroscopy measurement approximately 4 min post irradiation on a single crystal high purity germanium (HPGe) detector at WSU. The other two specimens and the fluence monitors were sent to PNNL for gamma spectroscopy measurements beginning approximately 6 hours post irradiation. At PNNL, one specimen was measured on a direct simultaneous measurement (DSM) detector system and one specimen was measured on one of several single crystal HPGe detectors. Specimens continued to be measured at semi-regular intervals up to 1 week post irradiation. The neutron fluence in each energy spectra was evaluated with the neutron fluence monitors and ranges

of fluence values were produced for each energy spectrum. MCNP models using these neutron fluence energy spectra were able to predict reaction rates in agreement with those observed in the fluence monitors.

4. RESULTS

This work adapts the modular Bayesian approach to estimate FPY uncertainties using gamma spectra data from irradiated specimens alongside radiation transport and detector response models. The workflow is unique compared to previous applications using Bayesian IUQ thus requiring novel approaches. The initial approach outlined here examines the ^{235}U specimen in the fission spectrum. From this specimen we analyse only a single decay chain and compares the activity of those radionuclides determined from experimental gamma spectroscopy measurements with the activities predicted by burnup models. For demonstration purposes we select the A=147 chain focusing specifically on the activity of ^{147}Pr as this radionuclide demonstrates the largest predicted activity within the chain during early gamma spectra measurements. The various components of the workflow are discussed in more detail below.

4.1. Serpent Burnup Model and Gaussian Process Surrogate

Serpent [11] is a continuous energy Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code used for many applications. One capability includes burnup calculations which combines neutron transport and decay simulations. The burnup model replicates the pulsed irradiation of specimens in the TRIGA reactor and their subsequent decay. It is constructed using available information from the experimental data description. The neutron fluence energy spectra for the D8 position of the WSU TRIGA reactor was provided by PNNL in cadmium and boron carbide containers. The burnup model consists of sealed specimens subjected to this neutron fluence followed by decay steps matching the timing of gamma spectra measurements. The model predicts the activity of each radionuclide in the A=147 chain following the reactor pulse and at each measurement time step. During this analysis we examine only the activity predicted for ^{147}Pr at 5 minutes post irradiation. The model's ability to accurately predict the number of fissions produced in the specimen is the current focus for model improvement. Collaboration is ongoing to enhance this critical aspect of model performance.

Sampling Nuclear Data and Uncertainty (SANDY) [12] provides a tool to sample nuclear data from ENDF-6 formats then rewrite perturbed ENDF-6 files used by nuclear codes. This tool enabled a sensitivity analysis using Sobol indices to determine the contribution of each radionuclide's independent FPY to the variance in the predicted activity of ^{147}Pr at 5 minutes post irradiation. The radionuclides with large sensitivities shown in Fig. 3 match those radionuclides with larger fission yields in the predominant energy range of the fission neutron spectrum. These results indicate only 5 sensitive parameters, allowing the others to be fixed. It should be noted that this analysis assumes independence in the input parameters which does not reflect reality. Though ENDF/B does not currently provide covariance information, it can be produced with SANDY or obtained from JEFF for use in a future analysis.

Training and testing data sets were generated from the Serpent model. SANDY was used to perturb the independent FPY data and write it into ENDF-6 format before they were passed to Serpent. A Gaussian Process (GP) surrogate model taking the 5 previously identified input parameters was trained and validated using 512 training sites. The comparison of surrogate predictions to test data in Fig. 4 indicates reasonable performance.

4.2. Gamma Spectra Analysis

GADRAS-DRF [13] provides a suite of gamma spectra analysis tools. Previously, GADRAS-DRF was used alongside the experimental data discussed in Section 3 to perform gamma spectra decomposition [14]. Smith calibrated and benchmarked GADRAS-DRF models with the PNNL HPGe detectors.

Figure 3. Sobol main effects indices indicating the proportion of model variance attributed to each independent FPY identified by incident neutron energy (E) and product (ZAP).

Figure 4. Surrogate model parity plot with R^2 and root mean square error (RMSE) indicating reasonable agreement between GP surrogate model and Serpent burnup model predictions.

As discrepancies between predicted and experimental gamma spectra were larger than expected, several methods were proposed to improve the predictions. While bremsstrahlung from β^- was shown to be negligible, Accidental Coincidence Summing (ACS), True Coincidence Summing (TCS), and systematic errors were identified as potential causes of the discrepancies. A method of addressing each of these issues was proposed and shown to improve predictions, though some discrepancies remained.

Current efforts to quantify radionuclide activity of ^{147}Pr have not been in agreement with Serpent model predictions. While some of this issue stems from the Serpent model under predicting the number of fissions in the specimen, the complexity of unseparated gamma spectra is also a significant contributor. Several other radionuclides share photopeaks with ^{147}Pr at sufficient intensity to obfuscate the true activity. As a result, we use a synthetic experimental activity and uncertainty selected to be in near agreement with model predictions to demonstrate the IUQ process in the next section. A similar process might be used to identify levels of uncertainty in experimental data required to achieve desired levels

of uncertainty reduction in parameters of interest.

4.3. Preliminary Inverse Uncertainty Quantification Results

The initial IUQ analysis uses a uniform prior distribution extended over a large range proportional to the yield uncertainty reported in the ENDF/B-VIII.0. This approach reduces over-reliance on prior uncertainties that are based on expert opinion. However, other prior distributions and their effects on the posterior still need to be assessed. The posterior parameter distribution is sampled with an adaptive metropolis MCMC algorithm. Convergence is assessed with visual inspection of trace plots, all $\hat{R} < 1.01$, and effective sample sizes $> 2,000$. While these results only demonstrate the process, some observations on model and parameter behavior might be made. Examining the prior and posterior results in Fig. 5, we can see that this process produces correlation information for the parameters. We also see posterior parameter distributions that are better described by log-normal or beta distributions than normal distributions. As this method describes independent FPY distributions that produce model predictions in agreement with experimental data, there is currently no process to enforce normalization, charge and mass conservation, or odd-even pairing effects. However, a reliable data adjustment should produce independent FPY distributions covering values capable of meeting these requirements.

Figure 5. Joint pairwise plots with correlation in the upper triangle, and histograms along the diagonal. The green line separates input parameters from the predicted activity of ^{147}Pr at 5 min post irradiation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The modular Bayesian approach to IUQ is demonstrated for nuclear data adjustment of independent FPY uncertainties from experimental gamma spectra data in a single decay chain. Synthetic experimental data is used as a proof of concept to demonstrate the potential of the process. However, determining accurate radionuclide activities with quantified uncertainties from unseparated gamma spectra remains a significant challenge. Some tools that assist with this are provided in GADRAS-DRF but other methods may be required. Possible methods pairing Bateman decay equations with rates of change in photopeaks of radionuclides of interest might be developed. The current demonstration only uses a small portion of available data to inform a small number of independent FPY. Reformulation of the current

likelihood function may allow for a more comprehensive analysis.

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